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K. Nikias

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Sources for the history of Ithaca after antiquity

ca. 530–1500

‘It seems that, since the island was small, nothing of significance happened after Odysseus, and if something did happen, then History does not tell us.’¹

K. Nikias

To recognise that the history of Ithaca after antiquity has long been overlooked by the scholarship, as I have done elsewhere, is to diagnose a problem rather than to treat it.² More than one century ago it was noted by William Miller that ‘it is customary to find the statement that the island of Odysseus was “completely forgotten in the middle ages”’.³ Miller’s survey of the mediaeval sources remains the best treatment at hand, but the sufficient number of new sources which have come to light since, together with those which escaped his eye, together justify a return to the task. The cure for the prevailing disinterest in the history of Ithaca after antiquity must surely be sought through the promotion of the primary sources for

* My thanks are due to Dimitris Prevezianos, with whom this series has been conceived, for his counsel and help in making often difficult historiographical choices.

¹ Nikolaos Karavias Grivas, *Ιστορία τῆς νήσου Ἰθάκης ἀπὸ τῶν ἀρχαιοτάτων χρόνων μέχρι τοῦ 1849* (Athens: Φ. Καραμπίνη καὶ Κ. Βάφα, 1849), 68.

² As I have done in Kyriaco Nikias, Review of Petros Vlachos, *Εκκρεμείς λογαριασμοί της Ἰθάκης με την μεσαιωνική ἔσ' ενετική Ἱστορία (της)*, *Mediterranean Historical Review* 37, no. 1 (2022): 126–29; idem, ‘Class and Society in Ithaca under Tocco and Early Venetian Rule (1357–ca. 1600)’, *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* 47, no. 1 (2023): 54–70; idem, ‘The Governors of Venetian Ithaca’, *Annual of the British School at Athens* 118 (2023): 399–416.

³ William Miller, ‘Ithake under the Franks’, *The English Historical Review* 21 (1906): 513–7, 513.

the period which are the basis of historical research. To this end much is promised by the reopening of the historical archive of Ithaca, which has allowed us to reconsider the boundaries of the surviving sources for the island's history, especially through a treatment of the earliest administrative and notarial documents of the Venetian period.⁴ While these offer some insight into the history of the island into the sixteenth century, no known documents from the archive on Ithaca extend their reach into the period before Venetian rule. For the period after antiquity and before Venetian rule, the sources relevant to Ithaca are fewer and poorer in detail, and the various attempts to survey them have tended to selectivity over comprehensiveness.⁵ The series *REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE* seeks to make a contribution to this end through compiling a list and summary of the known published documentary sources, and those unpublished documentary sources which archival research has made it possible to identify. The form of presentation follows the standard practice of collecting summaries of large numbers of surviving documentary sources (in the German historiography termed *Regestenwerke*), that is, to describe the nature of the source, citing the original, editions, and the most relevant literature, and giving the most fundamental critical commentary.⁶ The first part of the *REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE* presented here covers sources from the period of Byzantine rule, beginning from the sixth century, through the fall of the southern Ionian to the Normans and extending the centuries of Latin rule until 1500 when the island was captured by the Venetians. Sources after 1500 which cover the formative first century of Venetian rule have been collected and presented following the same method

⁴ On the Venetian administrative documents, see my forthcoming survey: 'The Archive of the Venetian Administration at Ithaca', *Mediterranean Historical Review* 39 (forthcoming) (2024). The earliest notarial documents are presently under preparation for publication by this author.

⁵ Most notable are Miller, 'Ithake'; the lemma for 'Ithake' in Peter Soustal and Johannes Koder, *Nikopolis und Kephallënia [Tabula Imperii Byzantini, 3]* (Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1981), 168–69; Alexios G. C. Savvides, 'Notes on the History of Ithaca (Ithake/Theachi/Val de Compar/Serfent/Faskyu/Siyaki) in the Byzantine and Post-Byzantine Periods', *Journal of Oriental and African Studies* 25 (2016): 441–45. Other literature of narrower scope is cited among the sources below.

⁶ The sigla adopted in this series are provided below. On the model of the *Regestenwerke* see *infra* n. 12.

in this volume by D. Prevezianos as the second part of the series.⁷ It is hoped that this series shall contribute to promoting interest in the island, particularly among scholars of the region for whom Ithaca has long represented a lacuna.

The selection of sources

Since the object of *Regestenwerke* is to support further scholarship, and must gloss over large numbers of sources, it is customary to leave interpretive judgment for future study. However, it cannot be denied that the selection of sources already requires judgments of quality and relevance to be made. Collections of this nature require that somewhat arbitrary decisions be made to define boundaries and rules for inclusion and exception. The basic rule followed here has been that the source must expressly refer to Ithaca (whichever variation of its name this might be).

The more sensitive rule concerns the temporal scope of the collection. For Part One of the REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE I have sought to restrict myself to those quiet centuries which were in the mind of William Miller when he referred to the decline in historical interest in the island after antiquity.⁸ The rather more easily defined boundary is the *terminus ante quem*, which is conveniently provided by the arrival of Venetian rule in 1500, after which the sources are greater and more detailed, and have been surveyed by Prevezianos in Part Two of this series.⁹

The *terminus post quem* is, however, rather more difficult to define. It has been decided that the Roman sources should be excluded here — and left for another collection — on the justification that these are foremost concerned with the Homeric epic and Ithaca's place in the Homeric world as the homeland of Odysseus. Such sources have been omitted, since the task of exhausting all references of this nature from the Roman and Byzantine (let alone Italian) commentaries would be too great in view of the fact these are concerned with Ithaca primarily as a literary construction

⁷ D. Prevezianos, 'Ψάχνοντας για την Ιθάκη στις απαρχές της βενετικής κυριαρχίας: 1500–1600' [REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE, II], *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society* 1 (2023): 92–126 (hereafter cited as *RIH*, II).

⁸ *Supra* n. 3.

⁹ Prevezianos, *RIH*, II.

and not the history of the island as a real place, let alone its condition during the time of the commentators themselves, which is our primary object.¹⁰

Nevertheless I have not at all sought to avoid the Homeric theme by rule, one we must acknowledge was most important for its having promoted interest in the island through history. Some sources derivative of Homer and the ancient scholiasts have been allowed in with discretion, such as the lemmata of the geographical encyclopaedia of Stephanus of Byzantium (from ca. 530), which are the earliest sources included here. These, though concerned with the world of the ancient epics, exhibit a special concern with the geography of the island and give a useful indication of continuity of the problem of Homeric geography into the early Byzantine period, a theme which study of the later sources collected here shows remained in the minds of the island's rulers and early tourists for centuries after. Since some of the lemmata were not included in Soustal and Koder's survey of the Byzantine sources, and given the early travellers like Leake were keen tracers of the Byzantine reception of Homeric geography, they were considered too significant to leave out.¹¹ The choices made represent imperfect solutions but necessary treatments for the practical impossibility of total coverage.

¹⁰ Cf. 'Über die felsige u. wenig fruchtbare Insel aus byz. Zeit fast nichts bekannt; Erwähnungen Ithakes stehen zumeist in mythologischem Zusammenhang.' [Hardly anything is known about the rocky and rather unfertile island from the Byzantine period; mentions of Ithake are usually related to mythology.]: Soustal and Koder, *Nikopolis und Kephallēnia*, 168, listing some of these sources at 169, nn. 1–7. We can add some others. See an account of the Ithacan fleet of Odysseus by Constantine Manasses (ca. 1150) in I. Bekker ed., *Constantini Manassis breviarium historiae metricum* [*Corpus Scriptorum Historiae Byzantinae*, 33] (Bonn: Weber, 1837), 53–4. Some passages on Odysseus in John Tzetzes (12th century): T. Kiessling ed., *Ioannis Tzetzae Historiarum variarum Chiliades* (Leipzig: F.C.G. Vogel, 1826), 226 at 6.743 ('τῆς [τοῦ Ὀδυσσεύως] πατρίδος'), 352 at 9.741 ('Ἐλυσαν δ' Ἰθακήσιοι ἀσκὸν τὸν τῶν ἀνέμων'). Also, the Homeric commentaries of Eustathius of Thessalonica (12th century), on the Iliad in M. van der Valk ed., *Eustathii Archiepiscopi Thessalonicensis Commentarii ad Homeri Iliadem pertinentes*, 4 vols (Leiden: Brill, 1971–1987); and those on the Odyssey in E. Cullhed and S.D. Olson edd. *Eustathius of Thessalonica, Commentary on the Odyssey*, 2 vols (Leiden: Brill, 2022–3).

¹¹ Soustal and Koder, *Nikopolis und Kephallēnia*, 168–9. See sources 1–10 below.

Within the bounds set for the collection, while the aim has been to be comprehensive, some sources no doubt have escaped me. Following the practice of Byzantine *Regestenwerke*, documents which are cited in the older literature, which have since been destroyed, lost, or are otherwise untraceable (termed *deperdita*), have been included here.¹² To do otherwise would deny the reality that such citations or fragments are often significant for they are the only sources we might have for a particular period. Indeed the inclusion of such sources is important because what might long have been considered a *deperditum* may one day be identified by future archival research. This has indeed turned out to be the case for several sources, including some relating to the formative early Venetian period surveyed by Prevezianos in part two of this series.¹³ As far as the surviving sources are concerned, we cannot fail to observe that so many — especially the documents of the Latin period — merely mention Ithaca as part of the realms of the county palatine of Cephalonia, a fact which may seem to have

¹² The classic examples followed broadly here are *Regesten der Kaiserurkunden des oströmischen Reiches*, 5 vols, ed. F. Dölger (vols 1–4), edd. F. Dölger and P. Wirth (vol. 5) (Munich and Berlin, 1924–65); and *Les Regestes des actes du Patriarcat de Constantinople*, 7 vols, ed. V. Grumel (vols 1–3), edd. V. Laurent (vol. 4) and J. Darrouzès (vols 5–7) (Paris: 1932–91). The methodology of *Regestenwerke* is surveyed usefully in *Ἡ ἀνάγκη καὶ ἡ τεχνικὴ τῶν ἐπιτομῶν [Nécessité et technique des regestes]*, Σεμινάριο ἐργασίας: Μεθοδολογία ἔκδοσης, κατάσταση, καὶ προοπτικὲς τῆς ἔρευνας τῶν μεταβυζαντινῶν πηγῶν 2 (Venice: Ἐλληνικὸ Ἰνστιτούτο Βυζαντινῶν καὶ Μεταβυζαντινῶν Σπουδῶν & Centre d'études byzantines, néo-helléniques et sud-est européennes E.H.E.S.S., 2003).

¹³ Prevezianos *RIH*, II. Notable recent archival discoveries include a late-seventeenth-century Ithacan copy of the appointment of Costa Puiese as governor of Ithaca in 1536. This act of the Venetian Senate had been cited vaguely in the old literature, from a Cephalonian copy presumably since lost: C. N. Sathas, *Ἑλληνικὰ ἀνέκδοτα*, vol. 1 (Athens: Τύποις τοῦ Φωτός, 1867), ρλα' n. 2. In my recent compilation of a list of governors of Venetian Ithaca, my survey of the likely copies led me to presume the document to be lost: Nikias, 'The Governors', Supplementary Material, notes on Costa Pugliese (s.v.). Only by chance during a survey of the Venetian fragments at the archive of Ithaca in mid-2023 appeared a copy of the concession of 1536 in a dossier relating to a dispute over inheritance among descendants of the family Puiese (also Pugliese or Pouliezos): ΓΑΚ Ιθάκης, Αρχεῖο βενετικῆς διοίκησης, Fragments, Box 38, Documents attributable to governor Francesco Cologna (1686) [*Scrittura instando*], ff. 1010/1029v–1022/1041r. The Ithacan copy is now cited in Prevezianos *RIH*, II, source 15. Another discovery concerning documents relating to the privileges of the family Galati in the Latin period are described *infra* n. 18.

rather limited application for the historiography of the island itself (see sources 25, 26, 29, 35, 36, 37, 38, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 49). We must not forget, however, that the island is not always so listed in documents issued by the court chancelleries, where the abbreviating tendency of diplomatic shorthand obscures full titles with an ambiguous ‘etc’.¹⁴ Indeed Hopf comments in his travel diary that ‘even’ a passing reference to Ithaca among the realms of the count Richard Orsini in the *praktikon* of 1264 (source 26) is important, since it ‘answers the question, until that point undecided, to whom Ithaca belonged in the thirteenth century’.¹⁵ The same point can be repeated for later sources which offer information of the same kind, which, though modest, affirm the place of Ithaca among the Latin possessions of the southern Ionian. This cannot be taken for granted, as indeed indicated by the political instability which is the context for source 37, and by the frequency of Ottoman incursions (on these, see sources 41, 47, 48, 49). The other significance of collecting such sources where Ithaca is but cursorily mentioned is that they clearly show what Miller had conjectured on a narrower scope of evidence, namely the unbroken continuity of the use of the classical name for the island despite the appearance of variants during certain periods, like the notorious ‘Val di Compare’ in some but not all of the mediaeval Italian documents (see sources 19, 22, 24, 25, 30, 31, 33, 36, 37, 39, 40, 41, 48, 49).¹⁶ For this reason, I have noted in parentheses the

¹⁴ For such documents where Ithaca is in fact mentioned, see sources 25, 26, 29, 35, 36, 37, 38, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 49. The number of documents where Ithaca is left out is much greater. No doubt, for example, Ithaca is intended in the unnamed provinces of the realm in the formulation ‘Leucatem, Zefaloniam, Zacintum, et cetera loca patrimonii sui antiqui’: in a document of 1433, in C. N. Sathas, *Documents inédits relatifs à l’histoire de la Grèce au moyen âge*, vol. 3 [*Μνημεῖα ἑλληνικῆς ἱστορίας*] (Paris: Maisonneuve, 1882), 417. The omission of a citation to Ithaca in these documents merely underscores the importance of those where the island is expressly listed.

¹⁵ ‘Schon dieser Titel ist interessant, weil er die bisher unentschiedene Frage, wem Ithaka in 13. Jahrhundert gehört habe, löst’: Carl Hopf, ‘Reiseberichte’, In *Monatsberichte der Königlich Preussische Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin. Aus dem Jahre 1864* (Berlin: Königlich Preussische Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin, 1865), 225.

¹⁶ Miller, ‘Ithake’, 514. On the name question, see Dikaios Vagiakakos, ‘Ἐκ τοῦ τοπωνυμικοῦ τῆς Ἰθάκης’, *Ἐπετηοὶς ἐταιρείας βυζαντινῶν σπουδῶν* 29 (1959): 322–48.

precise variation of the name of the island in each source (excepting the earliest Greek sources which all use the classical name).¹⁷

Finally, it should be observed that certain types of sources have been intentionally excluded. Cartographical sources (maps, portolans, etc) have been left out for practical reasons, because an initial attempt to include them all revealed there to be many more available sources than the few which have been cited in the literature; we therefore leave a survey of cartography for future research. Two other sources of clear relevance have been left out of the REGESTA because I have considered them impossible to disambiguate on the basis of the known evidence, but it is worthwhile to mention them here in the hope that future research will enlighten us. The first is a concession of privileges by Leonardo III Tocco in 1403 — believed lost until I recently discovered a copy in Venice — which mentions a certain Efdochia (Eudokia), daughter of Nicolaus Galates (Γαλάτης), and is associated with the Ithacan family by the old scholarship.¹⁸ Nevertheless, the document instead concerns fiefs on Zakynthos and does not alone allow us to reconstruct any connection with Ithaca.¹⁹ Another document left out is a lost and undated chronicle of the island's history, referring to a tradition which held that the two earliest pre-Venetian settlers of the island were Konstantinos Messinēs and Nikolaos Tamizēos in 1488. This is cited

¹⁷ Note that I have reproduced the name exactly as parsed in the source, without changing the case; the genitive is used frequently.

¹⁸ The relevant sources are outlined on the basis of the old literature in Nikias, 'Class and Society'. This relied on several documents cited by the German historian Carl Hopf from the archive of Zakynthos, destroyed in 1953. These *deperdita* were discovered, by chance, during my recent research in Venice, surviving in copies of the seventeenth century in a bundle concerning disputes among descendants of the family Palagano in Zakynthos: Archivio di Stato di Venezia, Provveditori sopra feudi, b. 1168 ('Querella contro Chiaretta Pelegana dal Zante...'). Among many other documents survive copies of several grants under the Tocco, including the grant of 1403 cited by Hopf which confirmed privileges for Franculo Palagano and his wife Efdochia (Eudokia), daughter of Nicolaus Galates: *ibid.*, f. 203r–207r. These have not been included in this collection because the documents do not expressly associate the family with Ithaca: this problem is outlined in Nikias, 'Class and Society'. The discovery of other *deperdita* linking this gap must be hoped for future research.

¹⁹ See *supra* n. 18; and the other documents discussed in Nikias, 'Class and Society'.

by Karavias Grivas in his history of the island from a booklet found in a church on the island, now ruined, and which it has been impossible to retrace.²⁰ These documents should be left out until further research brings us greater clarity, just as we hope it shall uncover even more documents relevant to Ithaca which have been missed here.

Notes on the presentation

The sources are listed here chronologically, giving the dates of redaction for diplomatic sources, and the reconstructed dates of earlier events recounted by chronicles and the like (which are given in the presentation in square brackets, []). The dating of sources, where not certain, has followed the suggestions of the better editions. Where there are multiple editions, usually only the latest or better has been pinpoint cited. Since many of the earliest sources are not solely concerned with Ithaca, literature on the sources has been usually omitted which does not expressly concern the island.

Sigla

Fons. = name or description of source; *Ling.* = language of source; *Inc.* = incipit; *Orig.* = original, where diplomatic source; *Ms./Mss.* = main manuscripts; *Cop.* = other manuscript copies; *Ed./Edd.* = editions; *Trans.* = translations into modern languages; *Cit.* = citations, if source survives in citation only; *Lit.* = literature; *Chr.* = notes on dating. *Crit.* = critical notes.

Abbreviations:

ASG = Archivio di Stato di Genova; ASN = Archivio di Stato di Napoli; AST = Archivio di Stato di Torino; ASV = Archivio di Stato di Venezia; BnF = Bibliothèque nationale de France; Vat. gr. = (Codex) Vaticanus Graecus; ΓΑΚ-ΚΥ = Γενικά Αρχεία του Κράτους – Κεντρική Υπηρεσία

CSHB = *Corpus Scriptorum Historiae Byzantinae* (Bonn); *CFHB* = *Corpus Fontium Historiae Byzantinae* (Berlin); *AAV* = *Acta Albaniae Veneta*; *MEI* = *Μυνηεΐα Ἑλληνικῆς Ἱστορίας*; *Enc. Med. Chron.* = Dunphy (2010)

²⁰ Karavias Grivas, *Ἱστορία τῆς Ἰθάκης*, 70 n. 1. My questioning in pursuit of the manuscript has led me nowhere.

ca. 530

1. **Lemma for Alkomenai in a geographical encyclopaedia.** *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at α 216. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 75.14–16. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2006) = *CFHB* 43/1. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 95, 232, 263–6.
2. **Reference to the existence of a spring of Arethusa in Ithaca in a lemma for Arethusa in a geographical encyclopaedia.** *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at α 410. *Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 116.6. *Ling. Greek. Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2006) = *CFHB* 43/1.
3. **Reference to an island called Asteria between Cephalonia and Ithaca with a quotation of Homer (Od. 4.844–6) in a lemma for Asteria, a city in Syria, in a geographical encyclopaedia.** *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at α 501. *Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 138.11–2. *Ling. Greek. Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2006) = *CFHB* 43/1. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 117, 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 58.
4. **Reference to a place in Ithaca called Demos or Krokyleion in a lemma for ‘Demos’ in a geographical encyclopaedia.** *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at δ 65. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 228.9. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck and Zubler (2011) = *CFHB* 43/2. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 251–3.
5. **Lemma for Ithaca in a geographical encyclopaedia.** *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at ι 42. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 328.22–25. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck and Zubler (2011) = *CFHB* 43/2. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 42, and *passim*.
6. **Lemma for place in Ithaca called ‘Korakos petra’ with a citation to Homer (Od. 13.408) in a geographical encyclopaedia.**

Fons. Ethnica of Stephanus of Byzantium, at κ 155. *Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 372.15–6. *Ling. Greek. Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2014) = *CFHB* 43/3. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 179 n. 5.

7. Lemma for Krokyleion, an islet of Ithaca, with a citation to Thucydides (3.96.2) and the Homeric scholiast Herakleon, who describes Ithaca as having four parts, in a geographical encyclopaedia. *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at κ 226. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 386.7–10. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2014) = *CFHB* 43/3. Note the apparatus in Billerbeck and Zubler, 129 n. 326. *Lit.* Leake (1835), 49, who recognises the four modern departments of Ithaca with those described here; Kordosis (2007), 245–55.

8. Lemma for Kynaitha with reference to a city of the same name on mount Neriton in Ithaca in a geographical encyclopaedia. *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at κ 262. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 393.6–7. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2014) = *CFHB* 43/3; *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 105 n. 11, 107.

9. Lemma for Neion, a mountain on Ithaca, with a citation to Crates of Mallus in a geographical encyclopaedia. *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at ν 42. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 472.12–5. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2014) = *CFHB* 43/3. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

10. Reference to a mountain called Neriton, likely that in Ithaca, in a lemma for Nerikos, a city in Acarnania, in a geographical encyclopaedia. *Fons. Ethnica* of Stephanus of Byzantium, at ν 45. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Meineke (1849), at 474.2. *Ed./Trans.* Billerbeck et al. (2014) = *CFHB* 43/3. *Crit.* Reference to Ithaca supplied by Billerbeck and Zubler: ‘Neriton, wie den Berg <auf der Insel Ithaka>’, i.e. Νήριτον, ὡς τὸ ὄρος <Ἰθάκης>. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

Before 535

11. Ithaca listed in the province of Old Epirus (Παλαιὰ Ἠπειρος) in a table of administrative divisions of the Empire. *Fons. Synecdemus* of Hierocles, at 652/ιβ'. *Ling. Greek. Edd.* Bekker (1840) = CSHB 18/3; Parthey (1866); Burckhardt (1893); Honigmann (1939). *Lit.* Vagiakakos (1959), 325; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 105, 263. *Crit.* Note emendations in the apparatus in Burckhardt, 13; also see Bekker, 425; Parthey, 15.

After 565

12. Account of Odysseus of Ithaca in the war against Troy. *Fons. Chronicle* of John Malalas, at 5.41, 5.47, 5.51. *Ling. Greek. Edd.* Dindorf (1831) = CSHB 32; Jeffreys, Jeffreys, and Scott (1986).

After 630

13. Ithaca in a list of Mediterranean islands. *Fons. Chronicon Paschale.* *Ling. Greek. Edd.* Dindorf (1832) = CSHB 16, at 49.

[Before 907]

14. Conjectured reading of Ithaca (‘Et’êké) in an Armenian version of a list of the hierarchy of the sees of the Eastern Church. *Fons. Notitia Episcopatum* of the Patriarch of Constantinople Nicholas I Mystikos. *Ling. Armenian. Ms.* Vatican Library, Vat. arm. 3. *Ed.* No critical editions. *Cit.* Darrouzès (1981), 60–1. *Chr.* The *Notitia* are dated between 901–7: Darrouzès (1981), 55. The ms. is expressly dated to 1270: see Darrouzès (1981), 60. *Crit.* The reading of two toponyms in the Armenian manuscript is uncertain: Esonas and Et’êké; the latter has been conjectured as Ithaca in Conybeare (1896), 126; this reading rejected by Darrouzès (1981), 61 n. 1.

ca. 930

15. Ithaca as part of the *theme* of Kephallenia. *Fons. De thematibus* of Constantine Porphyrogenitus, book 2. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Pertusi (1952), 174–6; *Trans.* Haldon (2021), 191–2 with extensive apparatus, noting known errors here and in the *De administrando imperio. Lit.* Zakythinis (1954); Oikonomides (1965); Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Zapanti (1992–4); Tsatsoulis (2012); Savvides (2016).

10th century

16. Lemma for Ithaca in a lexicon. *Fons.* Anonymous lexicon, *Suda. s.v. Ling. Greek. Ed.* Bekker (1854). Note neither the lemmata for Mount Neriton and Odysseus expressly mention Ithaca.

After 1013

17. Ithaca in a list of islands. *Fons. Chronographia* attributed to Leo Grammaticus. *Ling. Greek. Ed.* Bekker (1842) = *CSHB* 31, 17.

[1085]

18. A ruined city called Jerusalem on Ithaca (‘Ιθάκη’), in an account of the death of the Norman conqueror Robert Guiscard in 1085. *Fons. Alexiad* of Anna Comnena, book 6.6. *Ling. Greek. Edd.* Schopen (1839) = *CSHB* 2; Reifferscheid (1878) = *CSHB* 3; Leib (1937); Reinsch and Kambylis (2001) = *CFHB* 40, at 179. *Chr.* Before 1150: see Reinsch and Kambylis (2001), 5–6, n. 24. *Lit.* Hopf (1867), 144; Lekatsas (1998), 150ff; Vagiakakos (1959), 342–3 citing the older literature; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Malamut (1988), 188, cf. 187; Kordosis (2007), 110–13, 265; Leontsini (2014), 59–60.

[1101]

19. Account of a Genoese attack on a Byzantine fleet off Ithaca (‘ual de Compar’). *Fons.* Multi-authored chronicle begun by Caffaro of

Caschifellone, *Annales Ianuenses*. *Ling.* Latin. *Mss.* BnF, lat. 10136 (oldest); ASG, Serie dei documenti restituiti dalla Francia, Ms. di Parigi, 2(3); British Library, Additional ms. 12031. *Ed.* Belgrano (1890), 118. *RHC Oc.* (1895), 68. *Trans.* Hall and Phillips (2013). *Chr.* late-13th century: see *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 68, 135, 238. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 513; Lekatsas (1998), 156; Vagiakakos (1959), 325; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9. *Crit.* According to Miller, this is the earliest attested use of the Italian name for the island ‘Val di Compare’.

[1148–9]

20. Account of a Venetian assault on the navy of emperor Manuel Komnenos around Asteris, an island between Ithaca (‘Ἰθάκη’) and Cephalonia, in 1148–9. *Fons. Historia* of Niketas Choniates, book 2. *Ling.* Greek. *Edd.* Bekker (1835) = *CSHB* 35, 114; van Dieten (1975) = *CFHB* 11/1, 86. *Chr.* Before 1204: Simpson (2006); Simpson (2013), 2–3. *Lit.* On the context, see Magdalino (1993), 137–40; and on Choniates’ sources for this passage, see Simpson (2013), 217; also cf. Lekatsas (1998), 155.

Before 1154

21. Description of an island identified as Ithaca (‘Thacou’) in the geography of Muhammad al-Idrisi. *Fons. Kitāb nuzhat al-mushtāq.* *Ling.* Arabic. *Ed.* Cerulli et al. (1970–84). *Trans.* [Latin] Sionita and Hesronita (1619), at 182, 189 [‘Thanu’]. *Trans.* [French] Jaubert (1836), vol. 2, 121. *Lit.* Lekatsas (1998), 155; Vagiakakos (1959), 325; Savvides (2016); Savvides (2017). *Chr.* Jaubert (1836), vol. 1, xxii. *Crit.* The Arabic gives ‘Faskyu’, which Jaubert interprets as Thacou, and Savvides as Thaku or Thakiu; in the Latin translation of 1619, the text gives ‘Thanu’, which is read as Ithaca in Soustal and Koder (1981), 168 (noting that this is perhaps ordinarily read as Othonoi). To read Othonoi here would be bizarre from context, given the 1619 ed. on p. 182 lists the main Ionian islands: ‘Corfos, Leocata, Thanu, Cefalonia & insula Chachet’ (the last a corruption for Zakynthos); both the significance of the islands and their order north-south supports the reading of Thanu as Ithaca. This is also

supported by the improved transliteration in the French translation by Jaubert (1836).

Late 12th century

22. Ithaca ('Fale de Compar') listed among main islands 'in the Greek sea' ('in mari Graeco ... Nomina autem quarundam principalium insularum); also mentioned (erroneously as 'Serfent') among three islands under the control of the Norman admiral Margaritone ('Serfent, quæ est Margariti, et aliæ duæ insulæ ... Chefeleine, et ... Jagent') where navigation is unsafe due to piracy; also a description of a town built by Robert Guiscard on Ithaca ('Fale de Compar'). *Fons.* Anonymous chronicle, traditionally associated with Benedict of Peterborough, *Gesta Henrici II. Ling. Latin. Mss.* British Library, Cotton Julius ms. A.xi (older); and British Library, Cotton Vitellius ms. E.xvii (later). *Edd.* Stubbs (1867), 203, also 198–9; Liebermann and Pauli (1885) (excerpted ed. only), at 128. *Lit.* Heyd (1879), 210 n. 3; Miller (1906), 514; Lekatsas (1998), 156; Vagiakakos (1959), 325–6, 346 n. 5; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Malamut (1988), 187; Dalché (1995), 60, 199, 201; Kiesewetter (2006), 327–9; Kordosis (2007), 113; Savvides (2016), 443. *Crit.* The account of the town built seems to have confused the sources and is perhaps unreliable: at Stubbs (1867), 203. *Chr.* See *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 698. Also see the closely related Chronicle of Roger of Howden: see source 24. On the error giving Serfent (Serifos) for Ithaca see notes on source 24.

1198

23. Ithaca ('Ithaki') listed among territories included in a grant of privileges to Venice by Constantinople. *Fons.* Chrysobull of Alexios III Angelos (surviving only in Latin translation). *Ling. Latin. Edd.* Tafel and Thomas (1856), 246–80 (*Privilegium Alexii III Imperatoris Constantinopolitani, concessum incliti domino Henrico Dandulo Duci*), at 264; cf. 278–80 (*Epimetrum pacti*), at 279; Pozza and Ravegnani (1993), 130. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kiesewetter (2006), 343. *Crit.*

Generally see Penna (2012), 62–4. The Latin translation of the name makes it clear the Greek original had Ἰθάκη.

Before 1202

24. Ithaca ('Fale de Compari') listed among Greek islands and described following the earlier account attributed to Benedict of Peterborough (above source 22). *Fons.* Chronicle of Roger of Howden, *Chronica. Ling.* Latin. *Mss.* British Library, Royal ms. 14.C.ii (oldest); Oxford, Bodleian Library, ms. Laud 582; British Library, Arundel ms. 69. *Ed.* Stubbs (1870), 159, 161. *Chr.* see *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 1289–90. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 58. Kiesewetter (2006), 327–9; Savvides (2016), 443. *Crit.* As in source 22, here the ms. also has 'Serfent' at the second mention (at Stubbs, 161), which ordinarily means Serifos: Markl (1966), 57. On the problematic interpretation, and emendation of 'Serfent' to read Ithaca, see Soustal and Koder (1981), 58; Kiesewetter (2006), 327–9. Kiesewetter makes a strong argument for a copyist's error, where the ms. should read *Fale de Compari* in the second instance as in the first. This chronicle is reliant on the anonymous *Gesta Henrici II* (source 22), but the description of a town in the *Gesta* is less detailed in the corresponding passage here, in Stubbs (1870), at 161: cf. source 22. Also see *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 1289–90.

[1259]

25. Ithaca ('Teachi') listed among the realms of Maio Orsini, noting that the island is today called 'Val de Compare' ('Theachi, el qual es clamado agora Val de Compare'). *Fons.* Chronicle of the Morea (Aragonese version), *Libro de los fechos et conquistas del principado de la Morea. Ling.* Aragonese. *Ms.* Lost. *Ed.* Morel-Fatio (1885), at 53 para. 239. *Chr.* End of 14th century: *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 376–7. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9 (citing by error the Old French version but the Aragonese was intended); Kiesewetter (2006), at 338ff. with a survey on the sources for Maio. *Crit.* This is the only version of the Chronicle which mentions Ithaca. Ithaca is not mentioned in the Greek versions of the Chronicle

edited by Schmitt (1904) and Egea (1996); nor in the French edited by Longnon (1911), or the Italian in Hopf (1873a), 414–68.

[1261–82]

26. Ithaca (referring to “Ἰθακησίους”) listed with other regions which had been part of the Byzantine province of Old Epirus (Παλαιὰ Ἠπειρος), and then part of the Despotate of Epirus, referring to the reign of emperor Michael Palaeologus (1261–82). *Fons. Historia Romana* of Nicephorus Gregoras, book 4. *Ling. Greek. Edd.* Schopen (1829) = CSHB 25, 110. *Trans.* [German] van Dieten (1973), 119, also 251 n. 201. *Chr.* Written before 1351: see Van Dieten (1973), 38.

1264

27. Ithaca (“Ἰθάκης”) listed among the realms of Richard Orsini, count palatine of Cephalonia, in a register of landholdings of the Latin bishopric. *Fons. Praktikon* of the Latin Bishopric of Cephalonia (‘Πρακτικὸν τῆς ἀγιωτάτης ἐπίσκοπῆς Κεφαλληνίας ... ἐπὶ ἄρχοντος μὲν κόντε Πρεκιάρδου...’). *Ling. Greek. Ms.* Destroyed: see Tzannetatos (1965), 4. *Edd.* Miklosich and Müller (1887), 16–67, at 44; Tzannetatos (1965), 68, lines 590–1. *Lit.* Hopf (1865), 225; Kiesewetter (2006), 341. *Crit.* No landholdings on Ithaca appear to be listed, but see comments on the register and the toponym Jerusalem in Lekatsas (1998), 153, 158; cf source 18.

1278

28. Ithaca (‘Ythache’) described as the scene of piracy against merchant sailors. *Fons.* Account of legal claims by subjects of Venice against crimes of piracy: ‘Judicium Venetorum in causis piraticis contra Græcos decisiones’. *Ling. Latin. Ed.* Tafel and Thomas (1857), 215. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 514. *Crit.* The reference concerns the robbery of the ship of Phylippo de Lapathia in the sea of Ithaca (‘ad pontam de Ythache’).

1295, January 31

29. **Promise from the count palatine of Cephalonia Richard Orsini to grant the castle Coroni in Cephalonia or the island of Ithaca ('castrum Coroni ... sive ... insulam Ytacy') to his son John and Marie, daughter of Anna Comnena and the Despot of Epirus Nicephorus, on the pair's marriage.** *Fons.* Grant by count Richard Orsini: 'in privilegiis scriptis in greco, sigillis'. *Ling.* Latin. *Orig. and Cop.* Greek original lost; citation and description survives in Latin letter from the King of Naples Charles II to Florent of Hainaut. On mss. see Lambros (1914), 414; Perrat and Longnon (1967), 126. *Edd.* Minieri Riccio (1892), 87–8; Lambros (1914); Perrat and Longnon (1967), 126–7. *Lit.* Hopf (1867), 354; Hopf (1870), 165; Chiotis (1863), 22; Miller (1906), 514; Lekatsas (1998), 161; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Asonitis (2005), 65, 81–2.

[Late 13th century]

30. **Ithaca ('Thiachi') listed among the realms held by the count palatine Richard Orsini in a later description of the estate of the Latin Bishopric of Cephalonia and Zante.** *Fons.* Petition of Francesco Gozzadini, Bishop of Cephalonia and Zante on the taxation of church land. *Ling.* Venetian Italian. *Ms.* ΓAK–KY, ms. 45, f. 252/325v; the folio appears to have been reversed, with the continuation on the recto. *Inc.* 'Ser(enissi)mo P(re)n(ci)pe[,] Sono 400 Anni in circa ch(e) Il Conte Rizzardo dell'Isola del Zante[,] Ceff(aloni)a e Thiachi, Investi la Chiesa Latina di molti beni, quali tutti hà fatto notare dentro in un volume di cartapecora...'. *Chr.* After 1657, date of last cited document. *Crit.* The petition is copied among a register of documents concerning church property, ff. 248–332 (perhaps an inventory of the 'volume di cartapecora?'), the oldest of which is from 1412: f. 238r.

1320, June

31. **Reply from the Venetian Senate to the ambassador of the count palatine of Cephalonia Richard Orsini asserting Venetian**

sovereignty over the islands of Cephalonia, Zakynthos and Ithaca ('vallis compari'). *Ling.* Latin. *Orig.* Lost? *Cop.* Survives in register of Senate: ASV, Senato, Misti, rub. 1, f. 77/75v. *Edd. AAV* vol. 1, 32; Cessi and Sambin (1960), 233; Giomo (1880), 93. *Lit.* Romanos (1895), 125; Miller (1906), 514; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Nicol (1984), 90.

1321

32. Ithaca ('Compar') passed by the traveller Symon Semeonis on a pilgrimage to Jerusalem. *Ling.* Latin. *Ms.* Library of Corpus Christi College, Cambridge, ms. 407. *Ed./Trans.* Esposito (1960), at 38. *Chr.* Ms. dates to 1335–52: Esposito (1960), 1–3. Travel from Venice on 28 June 1321, and leave Crete on 10 October, making date of travel through Ionian between July and September: *ibid.*, 7–8. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

After 1340

33. Ithaca ('Fale de Compar') in a list of islands 'in the Greek sea' ('In mari Græco'). *Fons.* Chronicle of John Brompton [Fitzhugh Chronicle]. *Ling.* Latin. *Mss.* Cambridge, Corpus Christi College, ms. 96 (earlier); British Library, Cotton Tiberius C.xiii (later). *Ed.* Twysden (1652), 1218. *Lit.* von Warsberg (1879), 96; Vagiakakos (1959), 325 n. 8; *Chr.* After 1340, before 1377: see *Enc. Med. Chron.*, 218. *Crit.* This chronicle is evidently reliant on Roger of Howden and the anonymous chronicle traditionally associated with Benedict of Peterborough: see sources 24, 22.

1357?

34. Ithaca included among the lands, together with Cephalonia and Zakynthos, given in fief by the Venetians to Leonardo I Tocco. *Fons.* Reconstructed concession. *Orig.* Lost? *Cit.* Morosini (1628), 94 (erroneously giving 1352 and referring to Carlo, not Leonardo); and others, listed in Zečević (2014), 186 n. 205. *Lit.* Zečević (2014), 41 n. 43, 186 n. 205. *Crit.* According to Zečević (2014), 175 (cf. 33), 'there is no

direct evidence’, and the concession has only been imputed on the basis of other sources, surveyed by her at 186 n. 205.

[mid-1370s]

35. Ithaca (‘Ιθάκη’) listed among the realms inherited by Carlo I Tocco on his ascension to the duchy of Leukas and palatine county of Cephalonia on the death of his father Leonardo I (ca. mid-1370s).

Fons. Chronicle of the Tocco of Cephalonia, at line 25. *Ling.* Greek. *Mss.* Vat. gr. 1831; Vat. gr. 2214. *Ed.* Schirò (1975), 222. *Chr.* Composed before 1429: Schirò (1975), 137–9; on the date of death of Leonardo I, Schirò (1975), 25–7; Zečević (2014), 177. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

1384, August 22

36. Ithaca (‘Vallis de Compare’) listed among the realms which had belonged to the late count palatine of Cephalonia Leonardo I Tocco.

Fons. Concession of the realms of the Tocco to Rainier Grimaldi by the Louis, Duke of Anjou and King of Naples, 22 August 1384. *Ling.* Latin. *Ms.* Archives of the Palace of Monaco, Archives secrètes, A 18, n° 9, pièce 1. *Ed.* Saige (1905), 505–10, 506. *Lit.* Zečević (2014), 50, 56 n. 60. *Crit.* In this grant Louis, Duke of Anjou, sought to confiscate the realms of the Tocco, who are here described as traitors (‘rebelles et proditores notorios’) in the unstable political conflicts over the inheritance of the Angevin realms in Greece. The concession never occurred and the county remained in the hands of the Tocco. See also source 37.

1387, July 19

37. Ithaca (‘Valle de Compare’) listed among the realms of the county palatine of Cephalonia claimed by John Lascaris Kalopheros.

Fons. Concession of fiefs to John Lascaris Kalopheros by Amadeus of Savoy, 19 July 1387. *Ling.* Latin. *Ms.* AST, Principato di Acaia, mazzo 3.1, fasc. 3. *Ed.* Excerpted in Jacoby (1968), 217, n. 177. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 515. *Crit.* In what Jacoby describes as a ‘vive déception’, Kalopheros clearly never took possession of the county, which he seems to have been granted to

Kalopheros by the Latin emperor of Constantinople and prince of Achaea Jacques des Beaux during an unstable period under the regency of Magdalena Buondelmonti, widow of Leonardo I Tocco: see Jacoby (1968), 211–2, cf. 207–9; the claim to the title appears in an earlier Catalan document of 10 February 1383 in Rubió i Lluch (1947), 590–1 (‘Johan Lascari es hom assats notable ..., e es comte de les illes de Jazant e de Sefalonia’, not mentioning Ithaca); and in another of 20 July 1387 in Cessi (1919), 47, doc. 15; cf. Jacoby (1968), 217, n. 176; also Zečević (2014), 50, 56 n. 60.

1389, August 21

38. Ithaca (‘Ιθάκη’) listed among the realms of the duchess Francesca (wife of Carlo I Tocco) in a record on the election of the bishop of Leukas. *Fons.* ‘Κωδίκιον τῶν συνοδικῶν παρασημειώσεων γεγονὸς ἐπὶ τῶν ἡμερῶν τοῦ παναγιωτάτου δεσπότη τοῦ οἰκομενικοῦ πατριάρχου κυροῦ Νείλου’, in the register of the Patriarchate of Constantinople under patriarch Neilos Kerameus. *Ling.* Greek. *Orig.* ‘Registre V 48, f. 53’: Darrouzès (1979), 161. Ed. Miklosich and Müller (1862), 139. *Cit.* Darrouzès (1979), 160–1 (Doc. 2870). *Chr.* Date of document slightly earlier than accepted date of marriage to Carlo in Zečević (2014), 178–9. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 515; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

1422

39. A description of Ithaca (‘olim Ithaca, et nunc Val di Compare’) in the account of the traveller Buondelmonti. *Fons.* Traveller’s account including descriptions of islands and maps (*isolario*): ‘Liber insularum Arcipelagi’. *Ling.* Latin. *Mss.* Ragone (2002). *Edd.* Sinner (1824), at 57. *Trans.* Excerpts in Bessi (2014), with Ithaca at 245–7. *Chr.* Ragone (2002); Bessi (2014), 229. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 515–6; Vagiakakos (1959), 326; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Kordosis (2007), 265–6; Bessi (2014).

40. A description of Ithaca ('Val di Compare') among the other Ionian islands in the merchant's handbook of Giovanni di Bernardo da Uzzano. *Fons.* Handbook for merchant trade: 'Pratica della mercatura'. *Ling.* Tuscan Italian. *Ed.* Pagnini (1766), 218. *Lit.* Heyd (1879), 210 n. 3.

1430, July 6

41. Response of the Venetian Senate declining to guarantee Venetian protection against Ottoman attack over the realms of the duchy of Leukas and county of Cephalonia, including Ithaca ('val de compare'), then held by Francesca after the death of Carlo I. *Fons.* Responses sent 6 July 1430 by the Venetian Senate to letters of the *bailo* and *capitano* of Corfu dated 14 June. *Ling.* Latin. *Ms.* Copied in the Senate register: ASV, Senato, Deliberazioni, Secreti, reg. 11, ff. 119/120v–120/121r, 120/121v. *Ed.* *AAV*, vol. 14, 82–5 (doc. 3377), 85–6 (doc. 3378); second document also in *MEI* 1, 191–2 (doc. 125) but the last paragraph mentioning Ithaca is omitted. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Zečević (2014), 114, 118–9 n. 148. See also *AAV*, vol. 14, 29–40 (doc. 3327); Thiriet (1959), 271–2 (doc. 2186), 275 (doc. 2201). *Chr.* On date of death of Carlo I, see Zečević (2014), 179–80.

1430, December 24

42. Ithaca ('Thiaci') listed among the realms of Carlo II Tocco. *Fons.* Unclear. *Ling.* Latin. *Orig.* Lost? *Cit.* Morosini (1628), 96; Buchon (1843), vol. 1, 319, n. 1. *Crit.* Title of Carlo II transcribed by Morosini as 'Karolus secundus Dei gratia, Dominus Artæ II, Dux Leucate, ac Comes Palatinus Ceffalenix Pthiaci, & Zacynthi'; no doubt Pthiaci is a misprint for '& Thiaci', though Buchon emends it to 'Ithace' (without having seen the ms.).

1433, March 15

43. Ithaca ('Ithacae') listed among the realms of Carlo II Tocco in a grant recognising him as a Venetian subject. *Fons.* Concession of privileges to Carlo II Tocco by Francisco Foscari, doge of Venice. *Ling.* Latin. *Cop.* ASN, according to Buchon 'Ex libro privilegiorum secondo f^o 40, verso', 'Ce privilège se trouve inséré dans celui qui fut donné en l'an 1458 à Léonard II.': Buchon (1843), vol. 2, 353; also ASN, Archivio di Tocco di Montemiletto, Privilegi, b. 1, perg. 47 (according to Zečević (2014), 119 n. 151); also copied in ASV, Senato, Deliberazioni, Privilegi, reg. 2, f. 17r. *Ed.* Buchon (1843), vol. 2, 350–2 (from the Neapolitan copy) ('Ithacae'); also *AAV* 15, 5–6 (doc. 3550) (from the Venetian copy) ('I'tace'). *Lit.* Morosini (1628), 96. *Crit.* Title of Carlo II given as 'Carolus secundus de Tocco, Artæ despotus, dux Leucatæ et comes palatinus Cephaloniæ, Ithacæ et Jacinthis'. *Lit.* Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9; Zečević (2014), 112–3, 119 n. 151. *Crit.* Related document of 14 March 1433 does not expressly mention Ithaca: *AAV* 15, 4–5 (doc. 3549). Other relevant documents cited Zečević (2014), 119 n. 151, also 43 n. 50. This grant renewed in 1458: see source 46.

[1448]

44. Ithaca ('Itaco') listed among the realms of Carlo II Tocco in an account of Venetian history in the year 1448. *Fons.* Chronicle of Stefano Magno, *Annali veneti e del mondo*. *Ling.* Venetian Italian. *Mss.* Biblioteca del Museo Correr, mss. Cicogna 3529–33. On the complexities of the mss. see Hopf (1873), xxiv–xxvi; Setton (1978), 329 n. 50; Schmitt (2005), 133–5. *Ed.* Hopf (1873b), 196. *Chr.* Before 1572 (death of Magno): Setton (1978), 329 n. 50. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 516. Also see source 48.

Before 1449?

45. Ithaca ('Itace') listed among the realms of Carlo II Tocco. *Fons.* Confirmation of privileges held by the family Ariano of Cephalonia; one of three documents copied 'dalli Privilegi concessi alla Famiglia Ariano'.

Ling. Latin. *Ms.* ΓΑΚ–ΚΥ, ms. 45, f. 16/33r–v. *Inc.* ‘Carolus Secundus Dei Gra(tia) Dominus Despotatus Arthe, Dux Leucade ac Comes Palatinus Cefalonie, Itace, et Zacynthi, universis et singulis tam present(ibus) qua(m) futuris, hoc confirmationis privilegiu(m)...’. *Crit.* Ithaca not listed in the other two documents (dated to 1424, 1430) copied on the same folio. *Chr.* Zečević (2014), 182.

1458, January 3

46. Ithaca (‘Ithacæ’) listed among the realms once belonging to Carlo II Tocco. *Fons.* Renewal of privileges to Leonardo II Tocco by Pasquale Malipiero, doge of Venice. *Ling.* Latin. *Orig.* ASN, destroyed; ‘Ex libro privilegiorum secundo f^o 40, verso’: see Buchon (1843), vol. 2, 353. *Ed.* Buchon (1843), vol. 2, 352–3. *Lit.* Miller (1906), 515; Zečević (2014), 43 n. 50. *Crit.* Title of Carlo II given as ‘Caroli secundi de Tocco, Artæ despoti, ducis Leucatæ et comitis palatini Cephaloniæ, Ithacæ et Jacinti’. Renewal of grant of 1433: see source 43.

[1479]

47. Ithaca (‘Θιάκην’), Leukas, and ‘Lophimon’ captured by the Ottoman fleet. *Fons.* Chronicle of Ottoman assaults between 1187–1571. *Ling.* Greek. *Ms.* Library of the Monastery of Saint John the Theologian of Patmos, ms. 286, ff. 35v–37r. *Edd.* Lambros and Amantos (1932), 56–8, at 57; Schreiner (1975) = *CFHB* 12/1, 513–6, at 514. *Lit.* Vagiakakos (1959), 323; Soustal and Koder (1981), 168–9.

48. Account of the Ottoman capture of Ithaca (‘Itaci’, ‘Itacha, ditta Vale di Compare’). *Fons.* Chronicle of Stefano Magno, *Annali veneti e del mondo*. *Ling.* Venetian Italian. *Mss.* See notes on source 44. *Ed.* MEI, vol. 6, 214–43, at 215–6. *Lit.* Lekatsas (1998), 170; Schreiner (1977) = *CFHB* 12/2, 520–1 (‘zeitlich ... nicht genau präzisiert’); Miller (1906), 516. *Crit.* Sathas’s transcriptions ‘careless’: Setton (1978), 329 n. 50. For a related Byzantine chronicle, see above source 47.

49. Ithaca ('Itaca' vel sim, 'val de compari') listed among the realms of Leonardo III Tocco in an account of the Ottoman aggression and capture of the southern Ionian islands. *Fons*. History of Theodoros Spandounes: *De la origine deli imperatori Ottomani.... Ling. Italian*. Ms. BnF, ms. italien 881; see Nicol (1997), xvii-xviii. *Ed.* Spandugino Cantacuscino (1551), at 12, 26, 27 (all 'Itaca'), 61 ('val de compari'); *MEI* 9, 138–261, at 143 ('Ithaca'), 149 ('Itacha'), 150 ('Itacha'), 166 ('Itacha'). *Trans.* Nicol (1997). *Lit.* Miller (1906), 515. *Crit.* The passage in *MEI* 9, at 166 corresponds to the 1551 ed. at p. 61, but with textual inconsistencies including substitution of 'val de compari' for 'Itacha'.

*

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²¹ Photographs of this manuscript were very kindly provided to me by Dimitris Prevezianos.

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CFHB = Corpus Fontium Historiae Byzantinae

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Abstract

This article presents a collection of sources relevant to the history of Ithaca after antiquity, spanning from the Byzantine period until the island's capture by Venice (ca. 530–1500). The sources are presented as an aid to further research, citing the manuscripts, original documents, together with the editions, and providing a basic commentary where necessary for the interpretation of the source. This comprises the first part of the series REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE which aims to collect documentary sources for the history of Ithaca.

Περίληψη

Το άρθρο αυτό παρουσιάζει μια συλλογή πηγών που αφορούν την ιστορία της Ιθάκης μετά την αρχαιότητα, από τη βυζαντινή περίοδο μέχρι την κατάληψη του νησιού από τους Βενετούς (περίπου 530-1500). Οι πηγές παρουσιάζονται ως εργαλείο για περαιτέρω έρευνα, αναφέροντας τα χειρόγραφα, τα πρωτότυπα έγγραφα, καθώς και τις εκδόσεις, και παραθέτοντας έναν βασικό σχολιασμό, όπου απαιτείται για την ερμηνεία της πηγής. Πρόκειται για το πρώτο μέρος της σειράς REGESTA ITHACAE HISTORIAE, η οποία έχει ως στόχο τη συλλογή τεκμηρίων για την ιστορία της Ιθάκης.